

THE INFLUENCE OF SELECTED FACTORS ON OXYGEN EFFICIENCY

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Abstract

Oxygen (aerobic) efficiency is one of the most important determinants of our physical ability, which in turn is the most significant aspect of the human body. Physical activity is very often connected with health and life long health care. The purpose of this article is to show how aerobic efficiency is affected by different lifestyles and predilections among groups selected by the researcher. This will enable the determination of those factors that influence oxygen efficiency.

Purpose. The purpose of this research is to establish how aerobic efficiency, being the most important determinant of physical activity, presents in the chosen groups of respondents and how it is affected by various factors.

Materials and methods. 30 respondents between the ages of 18 and 24 who study or work took part in the research. All of them claimed to pursue regular physical activity.

Based on the interview with the respondents several subgroups were indicated: males, females, smokers, non-smokers, consumers of alcohol and non-drinkers.

Table 1

GROUP	Females	Males	Smokers	Non-smokers	Alcohol drinkers	Non-drinkers
Number of people	14	16	11	19	13	17

Results. Research conducted for the purpose of this manuscript enabled the evaluation of how oxygen efficiency presented in the different groups selected for the purpose of this study. Respondents who took part in the research varied based on gender and use of stimulants.

- Cigarettes reduce the Fitness Index (FI) rate
- Males have a better FI rate than females
- Alcohol does not reduce the FI rate
- Those who smoke cigarettes have a lower oxygen efficiency rate than those drinking alcohol

Key words: oxygen efficiency, physiotherapy, Harvard step test, physical activity, lifestyle

Introduction

Over recent times in developed countries, fewer people feel the need to undertake physical activity. For most adults their only physical

activity during the day is the walk from the car to the office and later from the car to the house.

As a result of this we see a growing number of people, including young people, experiencing various metabolic diseases, and chronic back,

head and joint pains. There has also been an increase in the rate of obesity which leads to many diseases and impairs quality of life. [3]

A very important role in raising awareness among adults, young people and children are social campaigns showing the benefits of physical activity on human development, appearance and character. Undertaking any sports activity increases one's self-esteem, belief in one's ability and knowledge that only systematic self-improvement can produce the desired effects. This in turn will have a positive impact on one's behaviour at work, and also social and family relations. Many companies have observed the positive impact of physical activity on humans. They encourage physical activity by giving out free gym or swimming pool memberships which may suggest that there is a growing community awareness of the importance of physical activity in building quality of life. [8]

Oxygen (aerobic) efficiency is one of the most important determinants determining our physical ability, which in turn is the most significant feature of a human body.[6] Physical

ability is very often related health and lifelong health care.[12] The purpose of this research is to show how aerobic efficiency is affected by different lifestyles and predilections amongst members of groups selected for the purpose of this study. This will enable the determination of those factors that influence oxygen efficiency. [14,5,11,4], [13,16,7,10,2]

The purpose of this manuscript is to check how aerobic efficiency, being the most important determinant of physical activity, presents in the chosen groups of respondents and how it is affected by various factors.

Materials and methods

30 respondents between the ages 18 and 24 who study or work took part in the research. All of them claimed to pursue regular physical activity

Based on the interview with the respondents, several subgroups were indicated: males, females, smokers, non-smokers, consumers of alcohol, and non-drinkers

Tab. 2.

GROUP	Females	Males	Smokers and physically active	Non-smokers and physically active	Alcohol drinkers and physically active	Non-drinkers and physically active
Number of people	14	16	11	19	13	17

Research methods

Many methods can be applied to demonstrate oxygen efficiency; however the one chosen for this research is the Harvard step test because it is effective and easy to conduct.

Execution consists of stepping up onto a platform (51 cm high for men and 46 cm high for women) at a rate of 30 steps per minute over 5 minutes for men and 4 minutes for women. Stepping on to the platform follows a verbal command or sound signal. After the exercise the subject's hearbeats are counted for 1 minute, 2

minutes and 3 minutes. The heartbeat is measured for 30 seconds.

Based on the heartbeat count a fitness index (FI) is calculated as per the following equation:

$FI = \text{time until exhaustion in seconds} \times 100 / 2x$ (total heartbeats counted).

Coefficient FI is a specific indication of oxygen efficiency for the Harvard step test expressed in points. The table below represents efficiency grades based on points achieved during the test. [15,9,5,1,8]

Tab. 3.

No	Fitness Index	Rating
1	50-55	Poor
2	56-64	Low average
3	65-79	Average
4	80-89	Good
5	90 or highier	Excellent

Organisation and the course of the research

Research was conducted successively in May and at the beginning of June 2015. Most of it was overseen at the Medical University in Lublin.

Subjects willing to take part in the research were interviewed regarding their use of stimulants and physical activity which helped to determine their profile.

Prestentation of the results of the resarch

During the course of the research it was established that men have better aerobic efficiency then women.

Average FI for men equals 89 and for women - 76, where standard deviation for women is 8.125729046 and for men - 10.46900186.

For female subjects the result of the Harvard step test was average and for male subjects it was good.

Tab. 4. All female results

No	Time until exhaustion *100s	Hb after 1-1.5 min	Hb after 2-2.5 min	Hb after 3-3.5 min	FITNESS INDEX	Result
1	24000	60	39	38	88	good
2	24000	60	53	50	73	Average
3	24000	54	47	43	83	good
4	24000	53	43	40	88	Good
5	24000	57	47	44	81	Good
6	24000	65	49	47	74	Average
7	24000	56	42	40	86	Good
8	24000	51	49	45	82	Good
9	24000	75	59	48	65	Average
10	24000	62	58	55	68	Average
11	24000	65	60	54	67	Average
12	24000	51	50	49	80	Good
13	24000	61	57	51	71	Average
14	24000	63	56	54	69	Average
	average				76.8	Average
	FI standard deviation				8.125729046	

Tab. 5. All male results

1	30000	55	49	43	102	Excellent
2	30000	72	67	60	75	Average
3	30000	59	53	49	93	Excellent
4	30000	59	51	45	96	Excellent
5	30000	56	52	52	83	Excellent
6	30000	67	63	52	82	Good
7	30000	58	44	38	112	Excellent
8	30000	65	53	42	93	Excellent
9	30000	62	50	41	98	Excellent
10	30000	56	55	50	93	Excellent
11	30000	67	60	57	81	Good
12	30000	66	63	61	83	Good
13	30000	57	54	54	90	Excellent
14	30000	67	64	59	78	Average
15	30000	75	69	61	73	Average
16	30000	60	53	50	92	Excellent
average	89					good
	FI standard deviation 10.46900186					

Graph 1.

Comparison of results from cigarette smokers and non-smokers

Average oxygen efficiency rate for the non-smoking respondents' group totalled **84.32** and for the smoking group it totalled **81.55**. Both results are interpreted as **good**.

Readings from the standard deviation for both groups demonstrate that the non-smoking group was more diversified (result of 12.60093749) than the smoking group (8.394803588).

Tab. 6. Comparison of results from physically active smokers

1	24000	60	53	50	73	Average
2	24000	54	47	43	83	Good
3	24000	53	43	40	88	Good
4	24000	57	47	44	81	Good
5	24000	65	49	47	74	Average
6	30000	72	67	60	75	Average
7	30000	62	50	41	98	Excellent
8	30000	56	55	50	93	Excellent
9	30000	67	60	57	81	Good
10	30000	67	64	59	78	Average
11	30000	75	69	61	73	Average
					81.55	Good
	FI standard deviation 8.394803588					

Tab. 7. Comparison of results from physically active non-smokers

1	24000	60	39	38	88	Good
2	24000	56	42	40	86	Good
3	24000	51	49	45	82	Good
4	24000	75	59	48	65	Average
5	24000	62	58	55	68	Average
6	24000	65	60	54	67	Average
7	24000	51	50	49	80	Good
8	24000	61	57	51	71	Average
9	24000	63	56	54	69	Average
10	30000	55	49	43	102	Excellent
11	30000	59	53	49	93	Excellent
12	30000	59	51	45	96	Excellent
13	30000	56	52	52	83	Excellent
14	30000	67	63	52	82	Good
15	30000	58	44	38	112	Excellent
16	30000	65	53	42	93	Excellent
Average:					84.5	

Graph 2.

Comparison of results from physically active alcohol drinkers and physically active non-drinkers

Table 8. Comparison of results from physically active non-drinkers

1	24000	60	39	38	88	Good
2	24000	60	53	50	73	Average
3	24000	65	49	47	74	Average
4	24000	56	42	40	86	Good
5	24000	51	49	45	82	Good
6	24000	75	59	48	65	Average
7	24000	62	58	55	68	Average
8	24000	65	60	54	67	Average
9	24000	63	56	54	69	Average
10	30000	55	49	43	102	Excellent
11	30000	72	67	60	75	Average
12	30000	67	60	57	81	Good
13	30000	66	63	61	83	Good
14	30000	57	54	54	90	Excellent
15	30000	67	64	59	78	Average
16	30000	60	53	50	92	Excellent
17	24000	63	56	54	69	Average
average					79	Good
Standard deviation					10.56	

Tab. 9. Comparison of results from physically active alcohol drinkers

1	30000	59	53	49	93	Excellent
2	30000	59	51	45	96	Excellent
3	30000	56	52	52	83	Excellent
4	30000	67	63	52	82	Good
5	30000	58	44	38	112	Excellent
6	30000	65	53	42	93	Excellent
7	30000	62	50	41	98	Excellent
8	30000	56	55	50	93	bardzo dobre
9	24000	51	50	49	80	Good
10	24000	61	57	51	71	Average
11	24000	54	47	43	83	Good
12	24000	53	43	40	88	Good
13	24000	57	47	44	81	Good
Average 88.7						Good
Standard deviation 14.15						

Research demonstrated that those who drink alcohol have a higher FI rate than the non-drinkers, and that standard deviation for those

drinking alcohol equals 14.15 while for non-drinkers undertaking physical activity standard deviation equals 10.56..

Graph 3.

Comparison of results from physically active alcohol drinkers and physically active smokers**Tab. 10.** Comparison of results from physically active alcohol drinkers

1	30000	59	53	49	93	Excellent
2	30000	59	51	45	96	Excellent
3	30000	56	52	52	83	Excellent
4	30000	67	63	52	82	Good
5	30000	58	44	38	112	Excellent
6	30000	65	53	42	93	Excellent
7	30000	62	50	41	98	Excellent
8	30000	56	55	50	93	Excellent
9	24000	51	50	49	80	Good
10	24000	61	57	51	71	Average
11	24000	54	47	43	83	Good
12	24000	53	43	40	88	Good
13	24000	57	47	44	81	Good
Average 88.7						Good
Standard deviation 14.15						

Tab. 11. Results from smokers

1	24000	60	53	50	73	Average
2	24000	54	47	43	83	Good
3	24000	53	43	40	88	Good
4	24000	57	47	44	81	Good
5	24000	65	49	47	74	Average
6	30000	72	67	60	75	Average
7	30000	62	50	41	98	Excellent
8	30000	56	55	50	93	Excellent
9	30000	67	60	57	81	Good
10	30000	67	64	59	78	Average
11	30000	75	69	61	73	Average
					81.55	Good
FI standard deviation 8.394803588						

Graph 4.

The oxygen efficiency rate in the group of those who drink alcohol and undertake physical activity ranges between 73 and 93 giving an average of 81.55. This classifies the general physical efficiency of that group as good.

Respondents claiming to consume alcohol and undertake regular physical activity achieved an average result of 88.7 which demonstrates very good physical efficiency.

The comparison of standard deviation for both groups demonstrates that the efficiency rate for smokers is less diversified (8.39) than the efficiency rate for alcohol drinkers (14.15).

Conclusions

Research conducted for the purpose of this manuscript enabled an evaluation of how oxygen efficiency is presented in the different groups selected for the study. Respondents who took part in the research varied based on gender and use of stimulants.

The findings arising from the research conducted are as follows:

- Cigarettes reduce the fitness index rate. Subjects who smoked had a lower oxygen efficiency rate than the non-smokers. This is a result of the harmful impact of smoking tobacco on the respiratory system which has a primary role in the metabolism of oxygen metabolism in the human body.
- Males have a better FI rate than females.
- Alcohol does not reduce the FI rate. Research findings suggest that those who drink alcohol have increased oxygen efficiency compared to those who do not drink.
- Those who smoke cigarettes have a lower oxygen efficiency rate than those who drink alcohol. Subjects who regularly play sport and smoke have a lower fitness index rate than physically active alcohol drinkers. Such a state of affairs is mainly due to the negative impact of tobacco smoke on the respiratory system which is important for oxygen metabolism.

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